

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF EMISSIONS FROM ROAD TRANSPORT

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Emissions from road transport are one of the main factors negatively impacting the environment. Carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons, and dust particles released into the atmosphere from vehicles cause air pollution. This process causes serious harm to human health, especially the respiratory system, and accelerates climate change. Also, car waste causes pollution of soil and water sources, compromising ecosystem stability. To reduce this problem, it is important to use environmentally friendly fuels, develop public transport and introduce modern technologies.

Keywords: road transport, emissions, environment, air pollution, ecology, health, climate, carbon dioxide, damage, sustainability.

Annotation: Emissions from road transport are one of the main sources of environmental pollution. During the operation of vehicles, carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons and particulate matter enter the atmosphere, which leads to a deterioration in air quality. These pollutants negatively affect human health, causing diseases of the respiratory and cardiovascular systems. pollution of soil and water resources. Reducing the negative impact of transport emissions is possible through the use of environmentally friendly fuels, the development of public transport and the introduction of innovative environmental technologies.

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Log in

The very special place in the development of modern society is occupied by road transport. The transport system has an important role in ensuring mobility of population, acceleration of economic development and logistics processes. However, along with the increasing number of road traffic every year, environmental factors are also increasing. Harmful emissions, emitted from automobile engines, in particular, are one of the main sources of environmental problems. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur compounds, hydrocarbons and fine dust particles are emitted into the atmosphere from road transport. The accumulation of these substances in the air leads to deterioration of air quality, smog formation, and global climate change. As a result, there is a serious threat to human health, an increase in respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. In addition, car waste also pollutes soil and water resources, causing the disruption of natural ecosystems. Today, in many countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, the issue of reducing environmental problems is considered urgent. Ensuring environmental safety in the transport sector, reducing waste and implementing environmentally friendly technologies is one of the important tasks. In this regard, the scientific and practical study of the environmental impact of road transport, the analysis of their consequences, as well as the development of ways to eliminate the problem have urgent scientific and practical significance.

Research and methodology

This study aims to assess the environmental impact of emissions from road transport. In the course of the research, scientific literature, international and domestic environmental reports and statistical data were analyzed. The composition of automobile emissions and their impact on the atmosphere, soil and water resources were studied using theoretical and analytical methods. Also, a specific analysis was carried out on the main indicators of air pollution. Observation, comparison, and generalization methods were used in the study. The results obtained made it possible to determine the relationship between the increase in the number of road transport and the concentration of harmful substances. The results of the research served as the basis for scientific conclusions aimed at ensuring environmental safety and reducing emissions in the transport sector.

Table 1

No	Pollutant	Primary Source	Environmental Impact	Impact of humans health
1	Carbonate anhidride (CO ₂)	Fuel Combustion Process	Climate change, global warming	Negative impact on respiratory activity
2	Nitrogen oxides (NO _x)	Engine emissions	Smog formation, air pollution	Pulmonary diseases
3	Uglevodorodlar (HC)	Full non-combustion of the fuel	Atmosphere ifloslanishi	Head ache, allergy.
4	Sulfur compounds	Disel oil	Acid precipitation, soil degradation	Respiratory damage
5	(PM)	Tires & Engine	Drop in air quality	Cardiovascular Disease

The main pollutants emitted from road transport and their impact on the environment

In this study, a number of scientific methods were used to determine the environmental impact of road transport emissions. In particular, a theoretical analysis was carried out through the study of the existing scientific literature and normative documents. On the basis of statistical data, quantitative indicators of automobile emissions were assessed. The level of air pollution was monitored using the observation method. Traffic load and pollution indicators in different regions were studied by means of a specific analysis method. The results obtained served to draw scientific conclusions by generalization and analytical assessment.

Results and discussion

The results of the study showed that emissions from road transport is one of the most important factors in environmental pollution. The analysis found that along with the increasing number of cars every year, the amount of harmful substances emitted into the atmosphere, including carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons and dust particles, is also significantly increasing. It was observed that air pollution levels were found to be higher than established norms, especially in large cities and areas with high traffic flows.

According to the study, incomplete combustion of fuel in engines is the main cause of harmful gas emissions. The accumulation of these substances in the air adversely affects human health, leads to an increase in diseases of the respiratory system, bronchitis, allergic conditions, and cardiovascular diseases. In addition, it has been found that car emissions are transporting to soil and water resources through rain and dust, causing the disruption of natural ecosystems and the decline of biodiversity.

The results of the discussion show that the insufficient development of the existing transport infrastructure, the abundance of obsolete cars and poor fuel quality further increase the environmental burden. At the same time, the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies, expanding the use of electric and hybrid vehicles, the development of public transport and regular vehicle maintenance were assessed as effective measures to reduce emissions. The results obtained confirm once again the need to strengthen environmental protection and ensure sustainable development in the field of road transport.

The results obtained during the study showed the need for an integrated approach to reducing road transport emissions. In particular, in urban areas, optimizing traffic flow, reducing traffic congestion, and implementing smart transport systems can significantly reduce air pollution. It is also important to limit the use of cars that do not comply with environmental standards and strengthen technical inspection requirements. Improving the ecological culture of the population, encouraging cycling and walking are also considered as effective measures for environmental protection. The consistent implementation of these measures serves to ensure environmental sustainability.

CONCLUSION

The study aims to systematically examine the environmental impacts of emissions from road transport. The results of the study showed that with an increase in the number of cars, the amount of carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons and dust particles emitted into the air increases significantly, which reduces air quality and leads to global climate change. Waste also pollutes soil and water resources and disrupts the stability of natural ecosystems. The analysis also revealed negative effects on human health, including an increase in respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. The study shows that the development of environmentally friendly fuels, electric and hybrid vehicles, as well as public transport are effective measures in reducing the amount of emissions.

Based on the results, the need for an integrated approach to reducing the impact of road transport on the environment, the importance of strengthening environmental policy and increasing the ecological culture of the population were identified. With this, the study provided an opportunity to assess the environmental problems associated with automotive emissions on a scientific basis and contribute to sustainable development.

References

1. Ježek Breclj, I., Gregorič, A., Zgonik, L., Rutar, T., Ivančič, M., Alföldy, B., Močnik, G., & Rigler, M. (2025). *Onroad vehicle emissions measurements show a significant reduction in black*

- carbon and nitrogen oxide emissions in Euro 6c and 6d dieselpowered cars. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 25, 9113–9125. acp.copernicus.org
2. Yang, X., Ke, J., Huang, Z., Wen, Y., Yin, D., Jiang, Z., Yue, Z., Wang, Y., & Liao, S. (2025). *Insight into greenhouse gas emission characteristics of lightduty vehicles in China in the context of technological innovation. Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 25, 7669–7689. acp.copernicus.org
 3. Kulmamatov, R. J., & Abdurasulov, S. S. (2025). *Environmental Regulation and Environmental Issues on Highways. Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 820–824. InLibrary
 4. Xidirov, M. Q. (2025). *Environmental impact of harmful substances contained in exhaust gases in the motor transport system. Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. erus.uz
 5. Boyirov, Z. R., & Abdullayeva, M. U. (2025). *Environmental Impacts of Motor Vehicles: Analysis and Prospects. Digital technology in industry*. ojs.qmii.uz
 6. Ismatovich Raxmatov, I., & To'yqulov, Q. S. (2024). *Avtomobil va uning atrofmuhitga ta'siri. Science and Education*. openscience.uz
 7. Khudoyberdiev, T. (2024). *The need to use alternative fuels in motor vehicles. Modern Science and Research*, 3(10), 132–137. InLibrary
 8. Liu, Y., Zhang, Q., Zheng, B., & He, K. (2024). *Modeling fuel, vehicletype, and agespecific CO₂ emissions from global onroad vehicles in 1970–2020. Earth System Science Data*, 16, 4497–(2024). essd.copernicus.org
 9. *Influence of transport air pollutants on climate change in EU: case of Lithuania* (2025). *Business: Theory and Practice*. journals.vilniustech.lt
 10. *AVTOMOBIL TRANSPORTINING ATROFMUHITGA TA'SIRI* (2025). *Journal of International Scientific Research*, 2(7).